

Phase Diagram Studies of Charge-Transfer Complexes

RAM ADHAR SINGH*, (Mrs.) ANURADHA VARSHNEY and S. N. BHAT**

Chemistry Department, North-Eastern Hill University, Shillong-793 008

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The stoichiometry of molecular complexes in solid state has been determined by studying the phase diagrams of molecular complexes. Tetracyanoethylene forms 1:1 complex with anthracene, hexamethylbenzene and naphthalene; phenothiazine forms 1:1, 2:3 and 3:2 complexes with iodine whereas methylphenothiazine forms only 1:1 and 2:3 complexes; hexamethylbenzene and 1,5-diaminonaphthalene form only 1:1 complexes with halonils. *p*-Benzoquinone form 1:1 and 1:2 complexes with *p*-chlorophenol and *p*-bromophenol.

EVEN though considerable amount of information has been accumulated on the stoichiometry and equilibria of molecular complexes in solutions, very little is known about the same in solid state¹⁻⁶. Recently some workers have shown keen interest in the electrical properties of the charge-transfer complexes, but no attention has been given in the study of the composition of the complexes (i.e., by studying the phase diagram) in solid state⁶⁻¹⁰. In most of the cases, molecular complexes are equimolar in composition (that is what has been assumed to be!), but there are complexes of different stoichiometries which are more stable than the 1:1 stoichiometry⁹. So we have made an attempt to determine the stoichiometry of solid molecular complexes by studying their phase diagram of a few $\pi-\pi$, $\eta-\sigma$ and $\pi-\sigma$ complexes.

Experimental

The electron donors, namely, naphthalene, anthracene, hexamethylbenzene (HMB), phenothiazine (PTZ) and N-methylphenothiazine (Me-PTZ) and the electron acceptors, tetracyanoethylene (TCNE), chloranil (CA), bromanil (BA), iodanyl (IA) and iodine (I₂), were purified by the standard procedures¹⁰. 1,5-Diaminonaphthalene (DN) and *p*-benzoquinone, were recrystallized from ether, and *p*-chlorophenol and *p*-bromophenol from ethanol respectively.

Various compositions of donors and acceptors, covering the whole range of concentrations (mole fractions), were prepared by mixing the appropriate amounts of the samples and grinding them together. A small amount of solvent, ether (peroxide free), was added to it, and then the solvent was removed by evaporating it under low pressure. Care was taken to avoid moisture from the beginning. In the case of iodine complexes, the solid molecular complexes were also prepared by mixing the appropriate amounts of stock solutions and then removing the solvent. In addition to this, the composition of iodine was determined by iodometric estimation before and after the melting points were noted and

it was found that there were hardly any changes in the compositions below and above the melting temperature.

A small amount of sample was sealed in a melting tube and the melting point of the sample was recorded, using Gallenkamp 2425 Micro heating table Boetius-HMK 72/3827 melting point apparatus. The temperature at which the melt solidifies was also determined and the average temperature was used for plotting temp. vs composition of the donor for obtaining the phase diagrams (as described in the standard procedure¹¹). The error limit was $\pm 0.2^\circ$. In the case of phenothiazine-iodine system, the temperature at which the melt solidifies was determined from cooling curve and there was negligible difference between the solidification temperature obtained by cooling curve and the one obtained directly. So for all other systems, the average temperatures of melting and solidification (direct) were noted.

Results and Discussion

It is well known that the melting point of pure component decreases by the addition of small amount of another component (of different nature), and the presence of congruent composition (with congruent melting point) indicates the existence of a stable molecular complex¹². The phase diagram of aromatics-TCNE, and PTZ-I₂, MePTZ-I₂ and *p*-benzoquinone-halophenols are shown in Figs. 1, 2, 3 and 4.

1. *Tetracyanoethylene-aromatic complexes*: Tetracyanoethylene, which generally sublimes without melting, melts when donor is added to it and in the beginning the melting point of TCNE decreases with the increase in concentration of donor. The first eutectic of TCNE-naphthalene has the composition of 35 mole % (of naphthalene) and the temperature is 91.2° ; similarly the second eutectic has the composition and temperature of 80 mole % (donor) and 72.4° , whereas congruent compound with a stoichiometry of 1:1 melts at 98.3° (Fig. 1). It can be seen from the Fig. 1, that

* Chemistry Department, Banaras Hindu University, Varanasi.

** To whom all correspondence should be addressed.

Fig. 1. Melting point-composition diagrams of TCNE-Aromatic Complexes.

1. TCNE-Naphthalene (—○—○—○—);
2. TCNE-HMB (—●—●—●—);
3. TCNE-Anthracene (—△—△—△—).

all of them form 1 : 1 complexes. It has been reported in the literature that naphthalene-TCNE and anthracene-TCNE form 1 : 1 complexes^{13,14}, while HMB-TCNE forms 2 : 1 complex in addition to 1 : 1¹⁵. However, we could not detect any maxima in the plot other than the corresponding to 1 : 1 stoichiometry. It is possible that at high temperature, the 2 : 1 complex may not be stable in solid state. It is pertinent to note that no simple known fixed relationship exists between the stoichiometry of any of the intermediate components (like eutectic compositions) and their melting points. The area under the portion of congruent compound in the temperature-composition plot of TCNE-aromatics varies in the order of naphthalene-TCNE < HMB-TCNE < anthracene-TCNE. It is interesting to note that the ionization potentials of these donors decrease in the same order (naphthalene 8.12 eV > HMB 7.80 eV > anthracene 7.40 eV) and the enthalpies ($-\Delta H^\circ$) (in solutions) and the electrical conductivities (σ) (in solid state) of TCNE complexes of these donors increase in the same order. So from these data, we can conclude that the area corresponding to the congruent compounds (in the temperature-composition diagram) can give an indication of the relative strength of the complexes. The best thing in this regard is to determine the enthalpy, free energy and entropy of fusion of the complexes.

2. *Iodine-aromatic complexes* : Iodine melts at 133.3°. When a donor is added to iodine the melting point decreases and it continues to do so till the

first eutectic point is reached (Fig. 2). The congruent stoichiometries of iodine complexes of naphthalene, HMB and anthracene are 1 : 1 and their corresponding melting points are 64.5°, 126.1° and 134.1°. The area under the congruent compound in the temperature-composition plot vary in the order of naphthalene-iodine < HMB-iodine < anthracene-iodine. These results go in parallel with those of enthalpies of complexes (in solutions), which reflect on the stabilities of the complexes¹⁶.

Fig. 2. Melting point-composition diagrams of Iodine-Aromatic Complexes.

1. Iodine-Naphthalene (—□—□—□—);
2. Iodine-HMB (—●—●—●—);
3. Iodine-Anthracene (—△—△—△—).

3. *Phenothiazine-iodine complexes* : Phenothiazine (PTZ) forms two more congruent compositions of 3 : 2 and 2 : 3 (D : A) with iodine in addition to that of 1 : 1 (Fig. 3). It is reported in the literature that the electrical conductivity of PTZ-iodine system is maximum (0.05 Mho cm⁻¹) at a composition of 2 : 3 and the energy of activation is minimum (0.15 eV)⁸. From the Figure, it is clear that the area under the curve for this composition is maximum (compared to the other two) and the congruent temperature (157.2°) is minimum for this composition. So from these observations, we feel that in PTZ-iodine system, the 2 : 3 complex is more stable compared to the other two. Here it can be mentioned that in the case of PTZ-iodine complexes, the Seebeck coefficient is maximum (0.2 mv/deg) when the D : A is 2 : 3¹⁷ and it was verified later by Doi *et al*⁸. N-Methylphenothiazine, (MePTZ), on the other hand, forms only 1 : 1 and 2 : 3 complexes (Fig. 3).

Fig. 3. Melting point-composition diagrams of Iodine-PTZ Complexes.
1. Iodine-PTZ (—●—●—●—);
2. Iodine-MePTZ (—△—△—).

We could not detect any other complexes having stoichiometry of either 2 : 5 or 2 : 7 which are reported by Dix¹⁸. In this case also, the complex with a mole ratio of 2 : 3 has the highest electrical conductivity (0.71 Mho cm^{-1}) and the next highest conductivity is at 1 : 1 ratio (0.12 Mho cm^{-1})⁸. There is no conductivity maxima or even a break at the compositions of 2 : 5 and 2 : 7. N-Methylphenothiazine (ionization potential, 7.15 eV) should be a better electron donor compared to phenothiazine (I.P. 7.26 eV). However, the area under the temperature-composition curve for PTZ-iodine for 2 : 3 composition is more than that of MePTZ-iodine. From this it appears that PTZ-iodine complex is stronger than MePTZ-iodine complex. Similar observations are reported in the case of phenothiazine and N-methylphenothiazine complexes of tetracyanoethylene, tetracyanobenzene and tetracyanoquinodimethene¹⁹. The lower complexing ability of N-methylphenothiazine is explained in terms of steric interactions which result in increased folding of the molecule and corresponding reduction of the interaction of N-lone pair with π -electrons of the rest of the molecule^{20,21}. From the temperature-composition plot it appears that the stability of various PTZ-iodine complexes is in the order of 2 : 3 > 3 : 2 > 1 : 1. Similarly for MePTZ-iodine, the order seems to be 2 : 3 > 1 : 1.

From the phase diagram studies, it appears that PTZ and MePTZ form 2 : 3 complexes with iodine rather than $(\text{thiazine})_2^+ \text{I}_3^- + \frac{1}{2} \text{I}_2$, as suggested by Doi *et al*⁶, where they have claimed that the low electrical resistivities are due to the charge carriers generated by the incorporation of extra iodine into the complex cation radical pentaiodide. Here it is to be noted that earlier workers reported that their 2 : 3 complex melts at 72° , whereas our complex melts at 157.2° . However, in the absence of any crystal and molecular structural data, it is not advisable to come to any conclusion whether it is $(\text{thiazine})_2^+ \text{I}_3^- + \frac{1}{2} \text{I}_2$ or $(\text{thiazine})_2 \cdot 3\text{I}_2$.

4. *Halonil-hexamethylbenzene, 1,5-diamino naphthalene complexes*: Hexamethylbenzene forms only one type of congruent compound (with a stoichiometry of 1 : 1) with *p*-chloranil, *p*-bromanil and *p*-iodanil and their congruent melting points are 201.6° , 195.3° and 191.6° respectively. These results compare well with the earlier reports²². The area under the curves of congruent compounds in the temperature-composition plots are CA-HMB \approx BA-HMB \approx IA-HMB; in other words, the stability of these complexes in solid state seems to be nearly the same. Here it can be mentioned that the electrical affinity of these halonils are also nearly the same (1.37, 1.37 and 1.36 eV respectively)²².

1,5-Diamino naphthalene, like hexamethylbenzene forms only one type of congruent compounds (with 1 : 1 stoichiometry) with the halonils and their congruent melting points are 146° , 163° and 156° respectively. The area under the curves of congruent compounds in the temperature-composition plots are in the order of CA-DN > BA-DN > IA-DN. It can be seen that the area under the curve in the plot of temperature vs composition for halonil-HMB are less compared to halonil-DN. This goes in parallel with the ionization potential of the donor. Here it must be mentioned that 1,5-diamino naphthalene can behave as n as well as π donors.

5. *p*-Benzoquinone-chlorophenol and bromophenol: The crystal structures of *p*-benzoquinone-chlorophenol and bromophenol show that in case of 1 : 1 complex, the phenol and quinone molecules are stacked alternatively to plane in infinite columns and the columns are linked in pairs by H-bonds between phenol and quinone molecule²⁴. It is mentioned in the literature that in 1 : 2 complex, the component molecules are stacked plane to plane discontinuously, a quinone molecule between two molecules of phenol and they are held together by charge-transfer forces and there is H-bonding between phenol and quinone²⁴. The phase diagram studies of *p*-benzoquinone and *p*-chlorophenol and *p*-bromophenol show clearly that *p*-benzoquinone form 1 : 1 as well as 1 : 2 complexes with chloro- and bromo phenols (Fig. 4). From this it is evident that phase diagram studies can be used to know the stoichiometries of the complexes in solid states. The area under the curve (in the plot of temperature vs composition) for 1 : 1 complex of

Fig. 4. Melting point-composition diagrams of halophenol-*p*-benzoquinone complexes.
 1. *p*-Chlorophenol-*p*-benzoquinone (—●—●—●—);
 2. *p*-Bromophenol-*p*-benzoquinone (—○—○—○—).

p-benzoquinone-*p*-chlorophenol is very much less compared to that for 1 : 2. If we consider the area under the curve as an indication of the stability of the complex, it appears that 1 : 2 complex is more stable than that of 1 : 1. However, in the case of *p*-bromophenol-*p*-benzoquinone, it is the other way; i.e., 1 : 1 complex is more stable than that of 1 : 2. As it has been pointed out earlier, in the absence of enthalpy, free energy and entropy of fusion, it is not advisable to comment on the stabilities of these complexes.

Conclusion :

The data presented above, show that the stoichiometry of the complexes, in solid state be determined by the phase-diagram studies of molecular complexes.

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